

FILAMENT WINDING OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES: VALIDATION
OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we have studied a model to simulate windings in the CAD/CAM systems for any axisymmetric geometry. This model is also validated. An extension of the model is applied to non-axisymmetric and general tapered mandrels.

INTRODUCTION

In the winding process the most important elements are the mandrel configurations, the fibers orientation, their trajectories on the mandrel surface and the movement of the feed eye of the winding machine [1], [2]. For what concerns the trajectory of the filament, it is well known that, for every curved surface, the greatest winding stability is obtained following the geodesic lines. This technique is limited to the simplex components; for complex shapes it is necessary to use the non-geodesic trajectories [3], [4].

WINDING WITH A CONSTANT SLIPPAGE TENDENCY

A non-geodesic winding is stable and suitable if the slippage tendency of filaments is not greater than the slippage resistance caused by the friction. A satisfactory stability control can be obtained making the slippage tendency constant in every point. By indicating with ψ the angle formed by the main normal \vec{n} to the line Γ and by the normal \vec{n}_s to the S surface (Fig. 1), it is evident that on each unitary element of fiber a lateral $-T_c \sin\psi \vec{b}_s$ and normal $T_c \cos\psi \vec{n}_s$ force develop. In order to avoid the slippage it must be:

$$|T_c \sin\psi| \leq |T_c \cos\psi| \mu .$$

We define "slippage tendency" k the ratio between the lateral and the normal force:

$$k = T_c \sin\psi / (T_c \cos\psi) = \operatorname{tg} \psi .$$

The condition for winding stability along the non geodesic path can be expressed in the following manner:

$$|k| = |\operatorname{tg} \psi| \leq \operatorname{tg} \varphi = \mu ,$$

where φ is the dome/fiber friction angle.
The relationship between ψ , α , and r is [2]:

$$\operatorname{tg} \psi = \frac{(\alpha' r \cos\alpha + r' \sin\alpha) [1 + (r')^2]}{r r'' \cos^2\alpha - [1 + (r')^2] \sin^2\alpha} . \quad (1)$$

It is interesting to see that if $\text{tg } \psi = 0$, from equation (1) we obtain the Clairaut's equation of geodesics:

$$r \sin \alpha = \text{constant.} \quad (2)$$

GENERAL AXISYMMETRIC MANDRELS

The above mentioned theory can be successfully applied for the determination of the winding paths to be performed on general axisymmetric geometry mandrels.

In case of geodesic windings the path Γ is given by equation (2), which, $r(z)$ being known, allows to determine $\alpha(z)$. Afterwards, by using the differential equation relating θ to r and α [3]:

$$\theta' = \frac{[1+(r')^2]^{1/4}}{r} \text{tg } \alpha, \quad (3)$$

$\theta(z)$ can be obtained.

The non-geodesic windings can be studied by replacing the axisymmetric shape with a sequence of truncated cones, (Fig. 2). Since for a cone, whose tip angle is β , the following equations are drawn:

$$\begin{cases} r' = dr/dz = - \text{tg } \beta \\ r'' = d^2r/dz^2 = 0, \end{cases}$$

placing $\text{tg } \psi = k$, the equation (1) can be modified to yield:

$$\alpha' = \frac{\text{tg } \alpha}{r} (\text{tg } \beta - k \sin \alpha). \quad (4)$$

The problem can be solved on the i -th conical element by integrating the following system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d\alpha}{dz} = \frac{\text{tg } \alpha}{r} (\text{tg } \beta_i - k_i \sin \alpha) \\ \frac{d\theta}{dz} = \frac{\text{tg } \alpha}{r \cos \beta_i} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The slippage tendency k_i can be varied step by step on the discretised surface. Same results are presented in Fig. 3.

PROCESS VALIDATION

An indirect numerical model validation has been carried out by comparing the numerical results with those presented in Ref.[4]. In that work geodesic and non-geodesic winding paths were computed and validated by manufacturing a conical sample. It is possible to see the good agreement between the two data sets (Fig. 4).

Our own model validation is in progress. The main relevant steps are:

1. Friction coefficient measurement.

The friction coefficient (static) between the mandrel and a prepreg roving will be measured.

2. Winding simulation.

Non geodesic winding will be simulated. Slippage tendency smaller,

greater and close to those experienced in the previous phase will be selected.

3. Winding realization.

The same winding patterns will be practically attempted and their stability will be checked. The experimental results will be compared to those foreseen by the model.

NON AXISYMMETRIC MANDRELS

The methodology previously described can be applied to non-axisymmetric mandrels [3].

Let us consider a cylindrical mandrel, whose cross section is shown in Fig. 5. Such a solid can be thought as being composed by a certain number of different cylindrical panels. On each panel geodesic or non geodesic winding patterns can be computed considering the local bending radius (local cylinder radius). Then, by transforming the system coordinates, the calculated coordinates of the winding path points can be referred to the reference system, which in our case is centered on the mandrel axis.

Let us consider a truncated cone whose cross section is composed of different arcs. The surface of such a solid can be thought as composed by a certain number of conical panels properly matched; the axes of the cones will be parallel to the mandrel axis. In order to have perfectly matched conical surfaces, with non discontinuities, the relationship $\beta_m = \beta_{m+1}$ must be respected (Fig. 6). Since $\Delta r = \Delta z \operatorname{tg} \beta$ does not depend on the local radius, the resulting cross sections will be similar (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 5).

Now we can think the solid under study as composed of a sequence of truncated cones as shown in Fig. 7. On the i -th truncated cone of the m -th conical panel the following equations can be used:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{da}{dz} = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha}{r_i^m} (\operatorname{tg} \beta_i - k_i^m \sin \alpha) \\ \frac{d\theta^m}{dz} = \frac{\operatorname{tg} \alpha}{r_i^m \cos \beta_i} \end{array} \right. \quad (6)$$

For each conical element the input data are: β_i , the panels base radius $(r_i^m)_0$, the curvature centers for each panel (X_c^m, Y_c^m) . By solving this system it is possible to determine the n -th point of the filament path with respect to the mandrel axis:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \xi_n = (r_i^m)_0 \cos \theta_n + X_c^m \\ \eta_n = (r_i^m)_0 \sin \theta_n + Y_c^m \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

Relevant results of the method are shown in Fig. 8.

CONCLUSIONS

Equations have been presented for the computer simulation of filament winding of composite axisymmetric structures using general non-geodesic winding trajectories. An indirect validation of the model has been shown while experimental tests for a direct validation are still in progress. The methodology has been extended to non-axisymmetric variously tapered bodies. The mandrels surfaces must be non-concave, but this is not a restriction. In fact by using a thermoplastic matrix and a correct consolidation system it is possible to get items with

locally concave surfaces which would normally produce fibre bridging.

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- α : winding angle
- c : curvature
- r : radius in a cylindrical reference frame
- T : tension of winding
- μ : friction coefficient

Fig. 1 Geometry of a non-geodesic path.

Fig. 2 A general revolution surface.

Fig. 3 Winding simulations on a conical axisymmetric mandrel.

(a) The optimised winding loop with a constant winding angle $\alpha = 45^\circ$ is obtained for $k = 0.1425$.

(b) The winding after 5 loops.

(c) After 12 loops. (d) After 24 loops.

Fig. 4 Comparison of numerical results between (a) Wells-McAnulty [4] and (b) the present model.

Fig. 5 Cross section of a non-axisymmetric mandrel

Fig. 6 Different curvature conical surfaces joint.

Fig. 7 General tapered non-axisymmetric surface scheme.

Fig. 8 Winding simulation on a tapered non-axisymmetric mandrel.